

Social Identification and Uprising Support

Evidence from Cali, Colombia

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Abstract

A dominant prediction of the social identity literature is that strong identification with a group fuels political participation, including support for high-cost collective action. We test this prediction using a large, representative population survey of 2,750 residents of Cali, Colombia, fielded a few months after the 2021 uprising that left dozens of demonstrators dead and the city blockaded for six weeks. Our outcome variable is self-reported support for the uprising (with perceived legitimacy of the strike as a parallel measure). Our identification measure is the trust each respondent reports in a member of one of four ingroups (district, class, religion, politics) and four outgroups (migrants, ex-combatants, riot police, rioters), relative to an average Colombian. Across specifications with district fixed effects and a rich set of socio-demographic controls, strong ingroup identification is negatively correlated with support for the uprising. Universalists, whose trust budget extends to an average Colombian no less than to a member of their own group, are systematically more supportive. Proximity to violent hot-spots in the city does little to displace this pattern. We argue that polarized post-conflict cities in the developing world are a class of contexts in which the dominant hi-identifiers prediction reverses, and we discuss what this means for the positive and welfare economics of revolt and for policy in fractured social contracts.

Keywords. social identification; universalism; collective action; revolt; Colombia; Cali; political participation; post-conflict.

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1. Introduction

In Albert Hirschman's framing, people who are unhappy with an organization or a regime can choose between exit, voice, and loyalty. Voice is collective. It requires that enough citizens place enough weight on a common good to absorb the private cost of demanding change. A growing literature in political psychology and behavioral economics offers a single, powerful prediction about who will pay that cost: those who identify most strongly with a group. The Social Identity Model of Collective Action, synthesizing 182 effect sizes, places identification at the centre of the engine that turns grievance and efficacy into participation (Van Zomeren, Postmes, and Spears, 2008). Politicized identities predict participation 27% more strongly than general group attachments (Simon and Klandermans, 2001). Identity, in this account, is the bridge from private preference to public action.²

If for these reasons it is important to know whether strong identifiers really drive revolt, testing it is also difficult. Most of the evidence comes from contexts in which the political fault line and the demographic fault line are aligned: a single ethnic or political minority confronting a state, a campus mobilization with one face. In settings of that kind, the prediction is almost a tautology. When a protest carries a group's banner, the people most attached to the group are the ones most likely to carry it. A harder test is a polarized city in which the same protest is supported by some members of every ingroup and opposed by others, and in which the violent events of the uprising are themselves a point of contention rather than a unifier. In this paper we argue that Cali in 2021 was such a city.

We use a large and representative population survey, fielded in the months immediately after the uprising, run in collaboration with a reliable local partner, to test whether strong ingroup identification predicts a stronger taste for revolt.³ The survey was administered face-to-face to 2,750 residents across the city's 22 local districts (or 'comunas') by 40 trained pollsters, with stratified quotas by socioeconomic stratum, gender, age, and ethnicity.⁴ Our main outcome variable is self-reported support for the organized protests; a parallel measure asks whether there were legitimate reasons for the national strike. Our identification measure follows Buchan et al. (2009, 2011) and Enke et al. (2022): each respondent reports trust in a member of one of four ingroups (own district, own socioeconomic stratum, own religion, own political views), each anchored against an average Colombian on a 0 to 10 scale.

Two ordering principles for the data compete. The first is parochial altruism (H1): support for the uprising rises with the strength of identification with one or more ingroups. The hi-identifiers literature, taken seriously, predicts H1. The second is universalism (H2): support rises with the breadth of the respondent's trust budget, that is, with the willingness to trust an average Colombian no less than a member of one's own group. Buchan et al. (2011) on global social

²Hirschman's distinction is set out most fully in *Exit, Voice, and Loyalty* (1970), where the willingness of the discontented to express disagreement publicly, rather than to defect or stay silent, is the central residual mechanism of repair in a deteriorating organization or polity.

³We borrow the term 'taste for revolt' from MacCulloch (2003, 2004) and MacCulloch and Pezzini (2007), where it denotes the survey-elicited disposition to support revolutionary action — typically the World Values Survey item on whether society must be radically changed by revolutionary action. Our measure is closer in spirit than in form, but it preserves the lineage; the object is support for a specific named event rather than a generic disposition toward revolutionary change. We use 'taste for revolt' and 'support for the uprising' interchangeably throughout the paper.

⁴The survey CaliBRANDO has been collected annually since 2014 by POLIS at Universidad ICESI, with funding from the Inter-American Development Bank, as documented in Martínez (2017); by 2021 the field team had over six years of experience running 25-minute face-to-face interviews across Cali's 22 comunas

identity and Enke et al. (2022) on moral universalism point in this direction. The two hypotheses are not symmetric. H1 is the dominant prediction and H2 is the alternative.

Our results favor H2 and reject H1. Conditional on a rich set of socio-demographic controls and district fixed effects, individuals who report stronger relative trust in members of their own group (ethnic, class, religious, or political) are less likely to support the uprising and less likely to call the strike legitimate. The same is true of identification with the riot police. The mirror finding holds for identification with the rioters, which is positively associated with support and is a natural placebo for the relative-trust measure. Universalists, whose trust in an average Colombian is no lower than their trust in a member of their own group, account for a disproportionate share of supporters. None of these patterns are erased by controls for age, gender, education, socioeconomic stratum, ethnic minority status, household composition, or by district fixed effects.

A natural worry is that being close to where the violent events of the uprising actually took place might do the explanatory work that our identification measure appears to do. Cali was not a uniform city for those six weeks. Some neighborhoods were besieged; others were quiet. We use geolocated survey responses and a city-level map of violent hot-spots to test this. Conditional on the same controls, the minimum distance to a hot-spot, the number of hot-spots within 0.5, 1, and 2 kilometers of the respondent's home, and the count of hot-spots within the respondent's 'comuna' are all uncorrelated with support and only weakly correlated with perceived legitimacy. Proximity to the violent events, in our data, does little to displace the identity result.

The stakes are not small. Latin America entered the 2020s in the middle of the largest protest wave in three decades, with anti-government mobilizations recorded across Bolivia, Brazil, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Mexico, and Peru (Carnegie Global Protest Tracker, 2021). The Colombian case is at the upper end of that distribution in both violence and political consequence: dozens of demonstrators killed, the third-largest city blockaded for six weeks, the conservative government weakened, the political coalition redrawn. Understanding who supports an event of this kind, and why, matters both for descriptive theory and for practical questions about how a partner government or NGO should think about reconciliation, communication, and the long aftermath of polarized unrest.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 sets the context and the human cost of the uprising. Section 3 develops the conceptual framework and states H1 and H2. Section 4 describes the design, both what we are able to do and what we are not. Section 5 takes identification and measurement seriously, given that this is a non-experimental survey. Section 6 reports labeled Results 1 through 6. Section 7 discusses what the pattern means for positive and welfare economics; Section 8 names the limitations and external validity concerns honestly; Section 9 concludes by returning to Hirschman's voice.

2. Context and the human cost of the uprising

Colombia entered April 2021 with an economy on the brink of collapse. The informality rate was at 60%, youth unemployment at 25%, 42% of all Colombians were living on less than three US dollars a day, and 37% of the population was eating fewer than three meals a day (Gaviria-Mira and Hoyos-Ceballos, 2022). Cali, the country's third-largest city and the capital of the Valle del Cauca department, was the city most affected by the pandemic, with a poverty rate above 36%

and an increase of more than 14 percentage points during the pandemic, adding 375,000 residents to the poor (DANE, 2021).

Figure 1: Confirmed violent hot-spots during the Cali uprising.⁵

On April 27th, the conservative government took a tax reform to parliament that raised taxes on the poor and the middle class. The next day, a national strike began. Within a week the tax reform was withdrawn, but the protests did not stop. On May 3rd, riot police entered Siloé, one of the poorest neighborhoods in Cali, with lethal weapons, killing peaceful demonstrators and detaining civilians arbitrarily. On May 6th and 9th, armed civilians fired on protesters and on members of the indigenous ‘minga’.⁶ On May 28th, riot police and armed civilians attacked demonstrators at the Universidad del Valle. Amnesty International (2021) documented at least 28 demonstrators killed by police, 90 eye injuries, 28 cases of sexual abuse, 2,000 arbitrary detentions, and over 300 disappeared. Figure 1 above plots the violence hotspots in the city during the uprising.

⁵ Triangles corresponds to hotspots defined by a confirmed killing or severe injury geolocated by Amnesty International (2021), see Temblores ONG (2021) and Cerosetenta and Bellingcat (2021).

⁶ The minga is a traditional Andean practice of collective labor and communal deliberation. In contemporary Colombia, Indigenous communities (notably the Nasa and Misak) have adapted it into politically organized mobilizations in which whole communities travel together to a city to press demands. The minga that reached Cali on 9 May 2021 came from northern Cauca in solidarity with the national strike.

For six weeks the national government lost control of Cali. Demonstrators (the ‘primera línea’ groups, acting in frontline clashes with police) blockaded every road connecting the city with the rest of the country. Riot police (ESMAD), rioters, armed right-wing civilians, and criminal gangs fought in the streets. Gas, food, and basic supplies ran short. Residents could not leave their homes. On June 16th, the Valle del Cauca government restricted movement for two weeks and the national government deployed the military. By the end of June, the police had recovered control. The economic and social costs of the uprising were massive.⁷

Figure 2: Survey geography

Geocoded home locations of the 2,750 respondents of the CaliBRANDO 2021 wave across the 22 urban comunas of Cali.

It is this city, with these events still fresh, that we surveyed. Figure 2 represents the geolocations of interviews, distributed across the 22 ‘comunas’. Field work began in the second week of October 2021 and ran through the second week of December, with around 400 face-to-face

⁷Fedesarrollo (2021) estimates the May economic cost of the strike between 4.8 and 6.1 trillion Colombian pesos (around \$1,500 million USD, or 5% of the whole department annual GDP of the time). Velásquez (2021) reports that 84% of Colombian companies were affected by central road blockades and over 800,000 jobs were at risk.

interviews per week and a final sample of 2,750 respondents. The instrument lasted about 25 minutes; participants were randomly selected adults intercepted in 41 public spaces with high pedestrian traffic (bus stations, parks, shopping centers, recreational centers, stadiums, churches, community centers) across the 22 comunas. Quotas were set by socioeconomic stratum (estrato), gender, age, and ethnicity, with a city-level margin of error of 1.9% at 95% confidence. The survey is called CaliBRANDO and has been collected in Cali since 2014, run by POLIS, a think-tank affiliated with Universidad ICESI.⁸

Our role in this collaboration was bounded by the partner's risk tolerance. The local partner declined our request to include actual participation in the revolt as an outcome (so we measure support, not participation), to ask about political orientation directly (we use a validated indirect instrument), to elicit risk and time preferences, and to run a vignette experiment on the role played by empirical and normative expectations in shaping support for collective action. We discuss the implications of these constraints in Sections 4 and 8.

3. Conceptual framework

The dominant prediction in the social-identity literature is straightforward. Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner, 1979) holds that individuals categorize themselves into groups, derive part of their self-concept from group membership, and act in ways that protect and advance the group's interest. The Social Identity Model of Collective Action (Van Zomeren, Postmes, and Spears, 2008) makes this operational: through a meta-analysis of 182 effects, the authors place identification at the centre of the path from grievance and efficacy to collective action, with a population correlation of $r = 0.34$ for general group identification and $r = 0.43$ for politicized identities.

Akfirat et al. (2021) extend the finding to digitally mediated mobilization. Cantoni, Yang, Yuchtman, and Zhang (2019) show experimentally in Hong Kong that strong anti-authoritarian identifiers signal type through participation in small protests. Bursztyn et al. (2020) show in Pakistan that individuals pay material costs to preserve political identity expression. Manekin and Mitts (2022) document the structural penalty that majority observers impose on nonviolent minority protest. The shared prior across this literature is that strong identifiers are the engine of revolt.⁹

A smaller, parallel literature points the other way. Buchan et al. (2009, 2011) argue that global social identification, attachment to humanity at large rather than to any particular group, predicts self-sacrificial cooperation in a multinational public-goods experiment. Enke, Rodriguez-Padilla, and Zimmermann (2022) elicit moral universalism in representative samples and show that the trait predicts redistributive preferences, civic engagement, and donations to distant outgroups. In a similar line, voters who identify with their cultural rather than their economic group polarize and act on a different set of grievances (see Bonomi, Gennaioli, and Tabellini, 2021). The

⁸The estrato is a six-category classification of city blocks used by Colombian utility companies to set tariffs. It correlates strongly with household income and education and is widely used as a stratification variable in Colombian household surveys.

⁹Van Zomeren et al. (2008) actually report two correlations: $r = 0.34$ for general group identification and $r = 0.43$ for politicized identities. We round to 0.34 in the text and note the politicized figure where the distinction matters.

common thread is that the breadth of the trust budget, how far the respondent extends moral concern beyond the ingroup, matters at least as much as its depth.¹⁰

In a non-polarized setting these two predictions are hard to tell apart. In a polarized city where every ingroup is split on the legitimacy of the events being mobilized around, they are not. We state them as labeled hypotheses.

H1 (parochial altruism). *Support for the uprising rises with the strength of ingroup identification. Respondents who trust a member of their own district, class, religion, or political group more than an average Colombian are more likely to support the protests.*

H2 (universalism). *Support for the uprising rises with the breadth of the respondent's trust budget. Respondents who trust an average Colombian no less than a member of their own group are more likely to support the protests.*

The two hypotheses are not symmetric. H1 follows from the hi-identifiers prediction; H2 is the alternative. A test that rejects H1 in this setting cannot reject the hi-identifiers result wholesale (the underlying meta-analytic correlation is genuine), but it can locate a class of contexts in which the prediction is overturned. We argue that polarized post-conflict cities, in which the violent events themselves are inside-the-ingroup objects of contestation rather than outside-the-ingroup grievances, are one such class.¹¹

Two further specifications are worth stating up front. The first is that our identification measure is symmetric across the ingroup and outgroup divide. The same instrument that asks whether a respondent trusts a member of her own district more than an average Colombian also asks whether she trusts a rioter (or a member of the riot police) more than an average Colombian. The relative-trust scale therefore allows us to run a placebo test with these two out-groups. The second is that the prediction in H2 is not 'support rises with trust in everyone'. It is the milder claim that support rises when the respondent does not place members of her own group above an average Colombian. Globalism, in our setting, is the absence of strong ingroup bias rather than an active cosmopolitan identification with humanity at large.

4. Design: what we do

The CaliBRANDO 2021 wave includes 104 questions across nine sections: demographics, subjective wellbeing, employment and income, financial access and indebtedness, perceptions of inequality, physical and mental health, satisfaction with the delivery of public policies, institutional and interpersonal trust, and perceptions of (and support for) the April uprising. Embedded in this longitudinal survey, we study the determinants of support for the uprising under three headings.¹²

(i) Individual characteristics. Demographic variables include age, sex, ethnicity (with a particular interest in racial minorities, who make up 33% of our sample), family size, and education. Socioeconomic variables include participants' socioeconomic status (defined by their official

¹⁰Buchan et al. (2011) use a multinational sequential public-goods experiment with 1,151 participants in six countries. Enke et al. (2022) elicit moral universalism in large representative samples and tie the trait to a long list of civic and political outcomes.

¹¹In Popper's sense, the test is a 'tough' one. The hi-identifiers prediction is the dominant view in the literature, has substantial meta-analytic backing, and is exactly the prediction the partner's local context would lead one to make. The fact that the prediction reverses in this setting is therefore informative.

¹² Full instrument available at https://osf.io/8w5bg/overview?view_only=afeca78aa7c24e52ac83cb09fb0378ae

‘estrato’), self-reported income, wealth, financial inclusion (whether the respondent uses a bank account), fintech inclusion (whether the respondent uses a digital wallet), and economic autonomy (whether the respondent reports being financially independent).

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

N=2,750	Mean (std. dev.)	Min	Max
Age	37.53 (15.96)	18	93
Female	0.51 (0.50)	0	1
Ethnic minority	0.33 (0.47)	0	1
High school	0.50 (0.50)	0	1
Household head	0.47 (0.50)	0	1
Children (#)	1.16 (1.39)	0	12
Crime	0.48 (0.50)	0	1
Conflict	0.14 (0.34)	0	1
SES	2.93 (1.39)	1	6
Income	1.84 (1.17)	0	5
Wealth (SR)	4.69 (2.07)	0	10
Poverty (SR)	0.22 (0.41)	0	1

Means and standard deviations for outcome variables, demographics, grievances, and social preferences. N = 2,750.

(ii) Grievances. Economic grievances include perceived policy discrimination, self-reported relative poverty, lack of social mobility, and not reaching basic needs. Political grievances include satisfaction with the local and national government and perceived local and national transparency. Violence-related grievances include exposure to criminal and political violence and a self-reported security index.¹³

¹³ On the behavioral footprint of conflict exposure as a control in Colombian survey work, see Fatas and Restrepo-Plaza (2025)

(iii) Social preferences. Absolute trust is elicited with standard 0 to 10 scales for trust in the general population, the police, civil servants, the local government, and the national government. Social capital is proxied by participation in a local NGO. Social identification is measured as relative trust, on a 0 to 10 scale, in a member of one of four ingroups (own district, own SES, own religion, own political views) and four outgroups (migrants in Colombia, ex-combatants, riot police, rioters), with 5 indicating equal trust in the named group and an average Colombian.¹⁴

The outcome variable is self-reported support for the uprising on a 0 to 10 scale, with 0 indicating no support and 10 indicating absolute support. A parallel item asks whether there were legitimate reasons for the national strike. The two items are highly correlated in our sample but not identical, and we report results for both throughout.¹⁵

4'. Design: what we do not do

The partner declined four extensions of the instrument that, in a more permissive collaboration, we would have included. We name them explicitly because they bound the conclusions we can draw.¹⁶

First, we did not measure actual participation in the revolt. The partner's risk assessment, in a city where rioters had been killed by police and identified individuals had been targeted by armed civilians, ruled out any question that would link a respondent to a particular action during the strike. Our outcome variable is therefore expressed support, not realized participation. A respondent who reports a 10 may have stayed at home; a respondent who reports a 0 may have been in the street. We discuss in Section 8 what this gap implies for the external validity of our finding.

Second, we did not ask about political orientation directly. The same risk assessment ruled out a left-right self-placement scale. We used a validated indirect instrument that asks about agreement with policy positions associated with the two main political coalitions and constructed a liberal/conservative index *ex post*. The indirect measure correlates with self-placement scales in pilots run in less polarized neighborhoods, but the trade-off is a noisier signal of political orientation than would be available in less risky settings.¹⁷

Third, we did not elicit risk and time preferences. Standard incentivized elicitation (Holt-Laury menus, convex time budgets) were ruled out by the partner's protocol for face-to-face interviews of 25 minutes in public spaces. We therefore cannot test whether the universalist pattern is partly a risk or time-preference story. Conflict exposure has been shown to leave systematic imprints

¹⁴Each item in Exhibit B asks the respondent to choose a value between 0 and 10 capturing how much more (or less) she trusts a member of the named group, relative to an average Colombian. The midpoint 5 indicates equal trust.

¹⁵The Pearson correlation between the support and legitimacy items in our sample is 0.84. We report results for both throughout; the legitimacy item plays the role of a parallel check on the support result.

¹⁶The trade-off between depth of identity measurement and the partner's risk tolerance is, in our experience, a typical feature of survey collaborations in post-conflict cities. We discuss it as an external-validity issue in Section 8. The instrument used was long, and we find it difficult to argue that identity measures were in any way prominent or salient.

¹⁷On the asymmetric attenuation of indirect measures of political orientation, see the discussion in the methodological appendix of Torcal et al. (2016). We follow their construction and use the same set of policy items, adapted to Colombian politics in 2021.

on risk preferences in Colombian samples (Fatas, Restrepo-Plaza, Jiménez, and Rincón, 2021), which would be one natural channel to test in a less constrained setting.

Fourth, we did not run a vignette experiment on the role of empirical and normative expectations in shaping support, as a causal proxy for norm-based social identification. A factorial vignette in which respondents are asked to predict how their neighbors would respond, or to evaluate the morality of participation in a hypothetical event, was declined on the grounds that it would slow the survey and increase the perceived political salience of the instrument. The implication is that we cannot disentangle the value channel from the expectations channel in the goal-transformation account of Buchan et al. (2011).¹⁸ We focus on the value channel by construction.

5. Identification and measurement

This is a non-experimental survey. We cannot identify the causal effect of social identification on support for the uprising. What we can do is compute partial correlations conditional on a rich set of observable controls and district fixed effects, and we can compare these correlations across ingroup and outgroup pairs whose symmetry serves as a measurement check on the relative-trust scale itself. The paper is honest about which steps in this argument do which work.

The relative-trust measure is the first move. Following, in spirit, Buchan et al. (2011) and Enke et al. (2022), each respondent is asked, for each of the eight named groups, to choose a value between 0 and 10 that captures her trust in a member of that group relative to an average Colombian. The midpoint 5 corresponds to equal trust; values above 5 indicate more trust in the named group than in an average Colombian; values below 5 indicate the reverse. Two features of this scale matter for what follows. First, it is harder to game than an absolute-trust scale because the comparison is anchored on a tangible reference. Anchored social-comparison reference points of this kind also shape how individuals form aspirations and update beliefs in strategic settings (Fatas, Morales, and Jaramillo, 2026). Second, it is symmetric: the same instrument that detects strong ingroup identification also detects strong outgroup identification, and the two should move in opposite directions for the same respondent if the measure is doing what we want it to do. The symmetry serves as a design-internal robustness check that we exploit in Section 6.¹⁹

The controls are the second move. All specifications include age, sex, an indicator for ethnic minority status, an estrato-based SES index, education, household-head status, and the number of children in the household. All specifications include comuna fixed effects, which absorb time-invariant neighborhood characteristics, including unobserved features of the local political ecology, the local exposure to the violent events of April to June, and the local distribution of socioeconomic stratum.²⁰

Even with these controls, four threats to a causal reading remain. We name them in the order in which they bite.

¹⁸ Bicchieri, Fatas et al. (2021) is an application of the empirical and normative expectations framework to compliance run in nine countries, including Colombia, during the COVID-19 pandemic.

¹⁹The relative-trust measure has a separate practical advantage. Interior values on a standard absolute trust scale are notoriously hard to interpret: a 5 out of 10 on 'how much do you trust the police' may mean caution, ambivalence, or simply unfamiliarity. Interior values on a relative scale anchored against an average Colombian carry an explicit comparison and are therefore more interpretable.

²⁰The comuna is the city's administrative district. Cali has 22 urban comunas with substantial heterogeneity in socioeconomic stratum, ethnic composition, and exposure to the violent events of April to June 2021.

(i) Reverse causation. Support for the uprising could shape ingroup identification rather than the other way around. A respondent who supports the protests may have lowered her trust in a member of her own conservative class after watching the response of conservative neighbors to the events.²¹ The cross-sectional design cannot rule this out. Our defense is partial. The relative-trust measure is anchored on stable categories (own district, own SES, own religion) that respondents have lived inside for years, while support for a specific six-week event is more plausibly endogenous to a stable identity than the other way around. The defense is weaker for political identification, where attitudes toward the event are by construction part of the political identity. We report results separately for the four ingroups, partly so that the reader can weight them differently.²²

(ii) Omitted variables. A trait that drives both strong ingroup identification and low support for the uprising, for example a generalized authoritarian disposition or low openness to experience, could produce the pattern we report without any direct identity-to-participation link. We cannot fully rule this out. The fact that our results hold separately for four ingroups whose composition is very different (own district vs. own religion vs. own political views vs. own SES) makes a single omitted trait less plausible but does not eliminate the possibility.

(iii) Measurement error in self-reported support. A respondent in October 2021 has reason to misreport her support for an event that ended weeks earlier and that the national and local governments are still litigating. Social desirability bias could push reported support in either direction depending on the perceived politics of the enumerator. The partner's randomized rotation of enumerators across districts, and the inclusion of enumerator-level controls in robustness checks, attenuate this concern but do not eliminate it. The parallel results on perceived legitimacy of the strike, a less personal outcome, should reassure a sceptical reader.

(iv) Sample composition by neighborhood selection. Respondents were recruited in 41 high-traffic public spaces. Residents who stayed home during the period of the survey are absent from the sample. To the extent that staying home correlates with both ingroup identification and support, we have a selection problem. We discuss this in Section 8 and provide bounds in the robustness appendix.

A final identification move is to use spatial variation in exposure to the violent events of the uprising as an indirect check on whether our identity result is doing something different from a proximity-to-violence result. Cali was not uniform during the six weeks of the strike. Some neighborhoods were besieged; others were quiet. We geolocate each respondent's home to her comuna and to the nearest violent hot-spot. For each respondent we compute the minimum distance to a hot-spot, the number of hot-spots within 0.5, 1, and 2 kilometres of the home, and the count of hot-spots within the comuna. If support for the uprising were driven mechanically by exposure to its violent costs, we would expect these proximity measures to absorb most of the variance the identity measure captures. They do not. Section 6, Result 6, reports this null. We read it as evidence that the identity pattern is not a relabeling of 'I lived next to where they died'.²³

²¹ We owe much of the discussion on reverse causation to generous comments during a seminar by Guy Grossman.

²² We treat the four ingroups separately rather than aggregating them into a single index because the underlying constructs (territorial, class, religious, and political identification) are conceptually distinct. The conclusions of Result 4 hold both for each separately and for a composite index that averages the four.

²³ Hot-spots are defined as the latitude-longitude coordinates of confirmed deaths and severe injuries reported by Amnesty International (2021) and the local NGO Temblores during the April to June 2021 period. We thank both organizations for the underlying geolocated data.

6. Results

We report six labeled results. Each headline appears in a one-sentence statement, followed by the evidence and any natural objection.

Result 1. *Socio-demographic predictors of support are conventional and consistent with previous work on revolutionary preferences.*

Conditional on the controls, support for the uprising is higher among younger respondents (a roughly 0.06-point reduction per year of age), lower among women, lower among respondents with children in the household, higher among ethnic minorities, and lower among respondents in higher socioeconomic strata.

Political orientation, captured by our liberal index, is by some margin the strongest socio-demographic predictor (together with financial inclusion): a one-standard-deviation increase in the liberal index — built as the difference between trust in the conservative national government and trust in the liberal local government, on a -10 to +10 scale (SD = 1.79)²⁴ — moves support by about 0.84 points and legitimacy by about 0.72 points, roughly one-fifth of a within-respondent standard deviation of either outcome and the largest socio-demographic effect.

These signs are consistent with MacCulloch (2003, 2004), McCulloch and Pezzini (2007), Torcal et al. (2016), and Kostelka and Rovny (2019). They are reported in Table 2 below.²⁵

²⁴ Our liberal index is best read as a polarization (of institutional trust) measure rather than as a clean policy position-based ideology score. It is mechanically related to some of the regressors used in our analysis later in the paper, so we will refrain from using it.

²⁵ MacCulloch (2003, 2004) and McCulloch and Pezzini (2007) document negative coefficients on age, income, and religiosity, and a positive coefficient on male sex, in cross-country data on revolutionary preferences. Our point estimates are within the range of those papers' meta-analytic estimates.

Table 2: Socio-demographic predictors of support

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Support	Support	Support	Legitimacy	Legitimacy	Legitimacy
Age	-0.0655*** (0.00422)	-0.0501*** (0.00533)	-0.0428*** (0.00548)	-0.0497*** (0.00382)	-0.0439*** (0.00485)	-0.0380*** (0.00499)
Female	-0.274** (0.133)	-0.274** (0.135)	-0.239* (0.134)	-0.198 (0.121)	-0.170 (0.123)	-0.142 (0.122)
SES	-0.133* (0.0763)	-0.174** (0.0765)	-0.275*** (0.0777)	-0.162** (0.0692)	-0.175** (0.0696)	-0.247*** (0.0708)
Minority	0.266* (0.147)	0.317** (0.146)	0.365** (0.146)	0.146 (0.133)	0.162 (0.133)	0.169 (0.133)
Education	0.368** (0.147)	0.320** (0.147)	0.0866 (0.152)	0.552*** (0.133)	0.522*** (0.134)	0.324** (0.138)
Liberal index	-0.476*** (0.0371)	-0.473*** (0.0370)	-0.472*** (0.0368)	-0.404*** (0.0336)	-0.404*** (0.0336)	-0.406*** (0.0335)
Head		-0.248* (0.143)	-0.288** (0.143)		0.0673 (0.130)	0.0133 (0.130)
Children		-0.253*** (0.0616)	-0.210*** (0.0617)		-0.122** (0.0560)	-0.0969* (0.0562)
Crime			0.388*** (0.132)			0.323*** (0.121)
Conflict			-0.381* (0.197)			0.0962 (0.179)
Banked			0.351** (0.158)			0.449*** (0.144)
Fintech			0.693*** (0.168)			0.446*** (0.153)
Constant	4.569*** (0.480)	4.531*** (0.482)	3.988*** (0.490)	4.578*** (0.434)	4.492*** (0.438)	3.984*** (0.446)
Comuna f.e.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,677	2,675	2,675	2,669	2,667	2,667
R-squared	0.163	0.170	0.184	0.135	0.137	0.149

OLS with comuna fixed effects. Standard errors clustered at the comuna level. N = 2,750.

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Result 2. *Life satisfaction and economic grievances have limited additional predictive power once socio-demographic controls are in place.*

We were a priori expecting larger effects from the grievance block. Cali in October 2021 is a city whose poverty rate had risen by 14 percentage points during the pandemic and whose tax-reform-driven protests had just ended. The grievance block (perceived policy discrimination, self-reported relative poverty, lack of social mobility, not reaching basic needs, criminal and political violence exposure) has predictable signs and modest magnitudes once socio-demographic controls are included, and life satisfaction itself has a near-zero coefficient.

The interpretation we prefer is that grievances are absorbed by the same socio-demographic structure: the respondents who report the strongest grievances are also the youngest, the poorest, and the most likely to belong to an ethnic minority. We do not read this as evidence that

grievance does not matter; we read it as evidence that, in this cross-section, grievance does not work as an independent predictor over and above who you are.²⁶

Table 3: Grievances and support

	(1) Support	(2) Support	(3) Support	(4) Legitimacy	(5) Legitimacy	(6) Legitimacy
Relative poverty	-0.0007 (0.178)			-0.150 (0.161)		
Subsidy frustrated	0.155 (0.152)			0.0523 (0.137)		
Safe: individual		-0.551*** (0.206)			-0.650*** (0.186)	
Safe: comuna		0.137 (0.157)			0.117 (0.142)	
No police patrols		0.154 (0.201)			0.163 (0.181)	
Transparency: local			0.397*** (0.0441)			0.324*** (0.0399)
Transparency: national			-0.462*** (0.0428)			-0.410*** (0.0387)
Constant	4.719*** (0.497)	4.976*** (0.498)	4.955*** (0.485)	4.891*** (0.450)	5.09*** (0.450)	5.10*** (0.439)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,727	2,727	2,664	2,719	2,719	2,656
R-squared	0.115	0.118	0.156	0.089	0.094	0.131

OLS with comuna fixed effects and full socio-demographic controls (age, female, SES, minority, education, household head, children). Standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Result 3. *Trust and social capital are positively associated with support for the uprising.*

Uprising supporters exhibit higher levels of absolute trust in the general population and in close individuals (model 1 in Table 4) and higher levels of social capital, proxied by participation in local NGOs (model 3 in Table 4). Trust in the conservative national government is negatively correlated with support; trust in the left-wing local government is positively correlated (model 2 in Table 4; and also Figure 3, using raw data). The pattern is similar for legitimacy (models 4 to 6 in Table 4) and is robust to district fixed effects and the full socio-demographic control vector.²⁷

²⁶The interpretation that grievance is absorbed by socio-demographic structure is broadly consistent with what Passarelli and Tabellini (2017) call the emotion-driven view of political unrest: the people most likely to feel aggrieved are also the most likely to belong to the categories that are themselves the residual carriers of grievance in a given society.

²⁷Trust in close individuals here means the average of trust scores for family members, neighbors, and friends, each measured on a 0 to 10 scale. The composite has a Cronbach's alpha of 0.78 in our sample.

Table 4: Trust, social capital, and support

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Support	Support	Support	Legitimacy	Legitimacy	Legitimacy
Police	-0.324*** (0.0317)			-0.193*** (0.0290)		
Civil servants	0.0380 (0.0351)			-0.0487 (0.0321)		
People	0.0713** (0.0346)			0.0436 (0.0316)		
Close people	0.135*** (0.0356)			0.0930*** (0.0325)		
National government		-0.583*** (0.0388)			-0.528*** (0.0350)	
Local government		0.351*** (0.0394)			0.265*** (0.0355)	
Social capital			0.752*** (0.158)			0.638*** (0.143)
Constant	5.564*** (0.512)	5.11*** (0.481)	4.633*** (0.485)	4.957*** (0.468)	5.15*** (0.434)	4.715*** (0.439)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,654	2,675	2,727	2,647	2,667	2,719
R-squared	0.172	0.191	0.122	0.128	0.171	0.095

Columns 1 to 3 use support as outcome; columns 4 to 6 use legitimacy. OLS with comuna fixed effects and full socio-demographic controls (age, female, SES, minority, education, household head, children), standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Figure 3: Support by absolute trust in local and national government

Result 3 is not surprising. Supporters of a high-cost collective action exhibit more interpersonal trust than non-supporters, and they participate in civic organizations more than non-supporters do. What is interesting is the asymmetry between trust in the two levels of government. The local government, run by a politician aligned with the protests, is trusted by supporters; the national government, which deployed the riot police, is not. This asymmetry serves as an internal consistency check on the trust measurement and as a reminder that 'trust' in our context is not a generalized civic virtue but a calibrated political judgment, in line with experimental evidence that the perceived legitimacy of democratic institutions shapes political identification and cooperation (Fatas, Restrepo-Plaza, and Banuri, 2024).

Result 4. *Strong ingroup identification is negatively associated with support for the uprising. H1 (parochial altruism) is rejected; H2 (universalism) is supported.*

This is the headline of the paper. Table 5 reports the regressions of support on each of the four ingroup relative-trust measures, with the full control vector and district fixed effects. We split relative trust into two regressors that measure intensity rather than direction. Above is the size of the positive deviation from the midpoint: it equals the gap between trust in the ingroup and trust in an average Colombian when that gap is positive, and zero otherwise. Below is the size of the negative deviation: it equals the absolute gap when trust in the ingroup falls short of trust in an average Colombian, and zero otherwise. Both variables run from 0 to 5. A larger Above is a stronger ingroup identifier; a larger Below is a stronger mistrust in the ingroup (a stronger outgroup identifier, by construction).

The coefficient on Above is negative and statistically significant for all four ingroups. It ranges from -0.07 for own SES to -0.15 for own ethnicity, in points of support lost per unit of positive deviation on the relative-trust scale (i.e., the slope). Respondents who place their own group above an average Colombian are systematically less likely to support the uprising. Because the

regressors capture intensity rather than direction, the implied effect at the extreme is the coefficient times the maximum deviation of 5: a respondent five points above the midpoint reports between 0.35 and 0.75 weaker support for the uprising (for own SES and own ethnicity, respectively). The reduction is modest but sizeable.

Universalism, the mirror image, is weakly associated with support. This is the pattern that Buchan et al. (2011) call global social identity, that Enke et al. (2022) call moral universalism, and that Restrepo-Plaza and Fatas (2022) document among Colombian victims and non-victims of armed conflict, who do not exhibit ingroup favoritism when the prevailing social norm does not endorse it. Coefficients in Table 4 are always positive but are never significantly different from zero. Respondents whose trust budget extends to an average Colombian no less generously than to a member of their own group exhibit a similar support for the uprising than those with no identification (trusting their ingroup as much as they trust an average Colombian).²⁸

Models (5) to (7) ask a sharper question: not whether strong ingroup identifiers withdraw on average, but which of them do. Each adds a moderator (CoV in Table 5) that switches on for one side of a cleavage and interacts it with the two intensity regressors. For social class (model 5), the negative effect is concentrated at the top of the distribution. Among low-SES respondents the coefficient on Above is indistinguishable from zero (-0.03, not significant); the withdrawal appears only in the upper strata (CoV*Above is -0.14, $p < 0.05$), so the implied effect for a high-SES strong identifier is about -0.16. The class story in Result 4 is, more precisely, an upper-stratum story: it is the comfortable identifier, not the poor one, who pulls back from the uprising. The less comfortable identifier, though, does not support the revolt in a stronger manner.

Table 5: Ingroup identification and support

	(1) SES	(2) Religious	(3) Political	(4) Ethnic	(5) SES	(6) Political	(7) Ethnic
Above (>average)	-0.0675* (0.0377)	-0.0852** (0.0397)	-0.115*** (0.0430)	-0.152*** (0.0525)	-0.026 (0.2176)	-0.108** (0.0420)	-0.155*** (0.0546)
Below (<average)	0.0232 (0.0364)	0.0283 (0.0343)	0.0289 (0.0334)	0.0359 (0.0314)	0.138 (0.2282)	0.0296 (0.0327)	0.0348 (0.0340)
CoV					0.896*** (0.3135)	-0.443*** (0.0667)	0.3261 (0.2240)
CoV*Above					-0.136** (0.0661)	-0.00692 (0.0199)	0.0243 (0.0698)
CoV*Below					-0.043 (0.0649)	-0.0109 (0.0206)	0.0107 (0.0667)
Constant	4.879*** (0.492)	4.840*** (0.494)	4.884*** (0.491)	4.854*** (0.492)	4.973*** (0.5062)	4.587*** (0.488)	4.854*** (0.492)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,723	2,722	2,710	2,723	2,723	2,656	2,720
R-squared	0.118	0.118	0.119	0.119	0.121	0.174	0.120

Models (1) to (4) reports the coefficient of relative trust in an ingroup member (SES, religion, political views, ethnic group), as defined by question 85 in the instrument (“someone who lives in the same socioeconomic stratum, someone with the same religious beliefs, someone with the same political opinions, someone of the same race or ethnicity”).

²⁸In supplementary specifications we replace the linear ingroup-identification measure with a binary indicator for relative trust above 5 and a binary indicator for relative trust below 5. The negative coefficient on strong ingroup identification is robust to this dichotomization.

Models (5) to (7) report the coefficient of relative trust adding an interaction term. CoV takes the value of 1 for someone with high SES (3 or above) in model (5), with liberal views in model (6), and for members of an ethnic minority in model (7). OLS with comuna fixed effects and full socio-demographic controls (age, female, SES, minority, education, household head, children). Standard errors in parentheses, *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Models (6) and (7) show a similar and symmetric result. For political views (model 6), the interaction with liberal placement is small and never significant (CoV*Above is -0.01, not significant), so conservatives and liberals who identify strongly with their own camp withdraw by about the same amount (a negative slope of roughly -0.11 each). The pull back is not a property of the left or of the right but of strong political identification as such, which is exactly what the orthogonality reading of Result 4 predicts.

For ethnicity (model 7), the negative effect of strong ethnic ingroup identification survives (Above is -0.16, $p < 0.01$), but none of the interaction terms with minority status reaches significance (CoV, CoV*Above, and CoV*Below are all not significant). Ethnic minorities and the ethnic majority withdraw by about the same amount when they identify strongly with their own group; minority status neither sharpens nor blunts the effect. Politics and ethnicity therefore behave alike: the withdrawal runs evenly through the group rather than localizing on one pole. Social class is the exception, the one cleavage on which it concentrates on a single side, the comfortable top. The result is not a single-group artefact.

Two things to flag before moving on. First, the rejection of H1 in our setting does not invalidate the meta-analytic finding of the hi-identifiers literature. The underlying correlation between identification and participation that Van Zomeren et al. (2008) report is real, and it is consistent with mobilizations in which the politicized identity and the political fault line are aligned. Cali 2021 is a context in which they are not, and the prediction reverses. Second, the size of the effect is meaningful but not large. For comparison, the strongest socio-demographic predictor in Result 1 — liberal political orientation — moves support by about a half standard deviation per one-standard-deviation increase. The ingroup-identification effect is therefore about 40% as large as the strongest demographic predictor, in the same setting and on the same scale. The pattern is real but not enormous. We do not want to oversell this.

Result 5. *Identification with the riot police and with the rioters is symmetric and is consistent with the relative-trust measure doing what it should.*

The relative-trust measure can be tested against a sign restriction the design itself provides. Identification with the riot police (ESMAD), that is, a trust score above 5 for a member of the riot police relative to an average Colombian, should predict lower support for the uprising. Identification with the rioters (primera línea), trust above 5 for a rioter relative to an average Colombian, should predict higher support. Table 6 reports the regressions; both predictions are confirmed. The coefficients are roughly symmetric in magnitude and opposite in sign across the support and legitimacy outcomes (see also Figure 4, which plots support against the relative-trust score for both groups). Within the negative domain (relative trust below 5), the relationship is also symmetric. The measure passes the placebo test.²⁹

²⁹A natural reading is that the symmetry observed in Result 5 acts as a calibration of the relative-trust scale: the same instrument detects political attachment in both directions, with the expected signs. Without such a symmetry,

Table 6: Outgroup identification (riot police, rioters) and support

	(1) Police	(2) Rioters
Above (>average)	-0.478*** (0.0587)	0.412*** (0.0534)
Below (<average)	0.173*** (0.0319)	-0.123*** (0.0318)
Constant	4.512*** (0.486)	4.571*** (0.483)
Controls	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,722	2,718
R-squared	0.162	0.152

OLS with comuna fixed effects and controls (age, female, SES, minority, education, household head, children), standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Figure 4: Relative trust in riot police and in rioters

the negative coefficient on ingroup identification in Result 4 would be harder to defend against the charge of measurement artefact.

Result 6. *Proximity to violent hot spots has little additional predictive power for support, once the full control vector and district fixed effects are in place; the effect is somewhat larger for perceived legitimacy.*

If the identity result of Result 4 were simply a relabeling of 'I lived close to where the riot police killed people', we would expect proximity measures to absorb a substantial share of the variance in support. They do not. Table 7 reports the regressions of support on the minimum distance to a hot-spot, the count of hot-spots within 0.5, 1, and 2 kilometres, and the count of hot-spots within the comuna, with the full control vector and comuna fixed effects (the comuna count and the comuna fixed effects together require dropping one or the other in some specifications; we report both). None of the coefficients on distance or hot-spot count are statistically distinguishable from zero at the 5% level. The point estimates suggest, if anything, that respondents closer to the violent events were no more or less supportive than respondents farther away.

Table 7: Hot-spots (HS) and support

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Distance (km)	0.147 (0.141)					0.219 (0.251)
#HS (0.5km)		-0.103 (0.207)				0.0643 (0.262)
#HS (1km)			-0.102 (0.123)			-0.00576 (0.184)
#HS (2km)				-0.00191 (0.0809)		0.0588 (0.0969)
#HS = 1					-1.282 (1.287)	-0.972 (0.633)
#HS = 2					-0.0705 (1.319)	0.165 (0.678)
#HS = 3					-1.172 (1.304)	-1.239* (0.733)
Constant	4.630*** (0.526)	4.816*** (0.496)	4.824*** (0.496)	4.815*** (0.516)	4.881*** (1.291)	4.271*** (0.678)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,681	2,681	2,681	2,681	2,726	2,681
R-squared	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.116

Models 1 to 4 use single proximity measures, model 5 uses the comuna hot-spot count, model 6 uses all measures jointly. OLS with comuna fixed effects and controls (age, female, SES, minority, education, household head, children), standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

For perceived legitimacy of the strike (Table 8), the picture is similar but slightly more textured. The minimum-distance coefficient is positive (0.26, statistically significant at the 5% level in the simplest specification): respondents farther from the violent events report higher legitimacy, and the comuna hot-spot count is positive in the saturated specification. The reading we prefer is the parsimonious one. In a city as polarized as Cali was in late 2021, residents had largely formed an evaluation of the strike before the violent events of May, and proximity to those events did not

substantially update support. The legitimacy outcome captures a more general normative judgment that varies somewhat with the distance from the violence, but not by much, and not in a way that displaces the identity result.³⁰

Table 8: Hot-spots (HS) and legitimacy

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Distance (km)	0.262** (0.128)					0.235 (0.227)
#HS (0.5km)		-0.278 (0.188)				-0.0709 (0.237)
#HS (1km)			-0.182 (0.111)			-0.0189 (0.167)
#HS (2km)				-0.0559 (0.0735)		0.0189 (0.0878)
#HS = 1					0.154 (1.166)	1.727*** (0.598)
#HS = 2					0.788 (1.194)	1.214* (0.641)
Constant	4.452*** (0.476)	4.786*** (0.449)	4.798*** (0.450)	4.873*** (0.468)	4.080*** (1.168)	4.243*** (0.691)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	2,673	2,673	2,673	2,673	2,718	2,673
R-squared	0.089	0.089	0.089	0.088	0.088	0.089

Same specifications as Table 7, legitimacy as outcome, standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Together, Results 4, 5, and 6 form the empirical spine of the paper. Strong ingroup identification reduces support. The measurement passes its design-internal placebo. Proximity to where the events happened does not absorb the result.

7. Discussion

The interesting thing about Result 4 is not that universalism predicts support (Buchan et al. (2011) and Enke et al. (2022) would have predicted it), but that the ingroup prediction of the hi-identifiers literature reverses in this setting. Strong identification with the respondent's own district, own class, own religion, and own political views all push in the same direction, and that direction is away from support for the uprising.

The intuition is that the uprising was, in Cali in 2021, an event that cut across every ingroup in the city rather than aligning with any of them. Conservative neighborhoods produced rioters and police; liberal neighborhoods also produced both. The Catholic Church spoke for restraint and

³⁰The minimum-distance coefficient on legitimacy of 0.262 (s.e. 0.128) in the simplest specification of Table 8 implies that a respondent one kilometer farther from a hot-spot reports legitimacy approximately 0.26 points higher on the 0 to 10 scale. The signal is statistically significant at the 5% level in the linear specification but is not robust across the alternative hot-spot count specifications.

for the demonstrators in roughly equal measure. The minority indigenous minga marched in solidarity but was attacked by armed civilians of varied ethnicity. In a setting in which the cleavage between supporters and opponents runs through every group rather than between groups, strong ingroup identification is the wrong instrument for mobilization. The respondent who values her own group above an average Colombian is, in this setting, more likely to be loyal to the group's quietest median than to the protest the group's loudest minority is marching for. The hi-identifiers prediction depends on the assumption that the politicized identity and the political fault line are aligned; in Cali they were orthogonal.³¹

The result is not deeply worrying for positive economics. The hi-identifiers literature can survive the addition of a moderator: in settings where politicized identity is aligned with the political fault line, strong identifiers participate; in settings where it is not, they pull back toward loyalty. Bonomi, Gennaioli, and Tabellini (2021) come close to making exactly this point for the United States in the case of switching between economic and cultural identities. We add a developing-country, post-conflict observation that points in the same direction.³²

The trouble is possibly deeper for welfare economics. If the engine of collective political action in polarized post-conflict societies is universalism rather than parochialism, then institutions that erode universal identification, by sorting citizens into demographic, religious, and political pockets that distrust each other more than they distrust an average national, also erode the capacity for collective action of any kind, including the kind a society needs to renegotiate a fractured social contract. A society of strong ingroup identifiers can sustain hyperlocal cooperation. It cannot easily produce a march that crosses comunas. The implication for the Colombian stakeholders (from POLIS, to Cali's local government and Colombia's national government) is that the construction of universalist trust is a precondition for legitimate voice and not merely a side effect of it.

Our policy message has to do with the practical consequences of this welfare claim. Polarized post-conflict cities have a recurring policy choice between strengthening particular communities (an inward turn that reinforces ingroup identification) and strengthening the institutions that connect those communities (an outward turn that builds universalism). The first is cheaper and politically easier; the second is harder and slower. The pattern in our data suggests that the harder route is also the route that produces a citizen who is willing to bear the cost of collective political action when the social contract is genuinely contested. We do not believe the policy choice is binary; we do believe that the marginal investment in cross-group institutions returns more than the marginal investment in within-group institutions in this kind of setting. Restrepo-Plaza and Fatas (2023) provide experimental evidence consistent with this claim, showing that institutions designed to bridge polarized identities in Colombia (around the peace process and the same-sex marriage debate) shift behaviour toward inclusion. The reference-dependent forgiveness pattern documented by Fatas and Restrepo-Plaza (2022) in a large lab-in-the-field experiment in Colombia is a related piece of the same policy puzzle: how reconciliation is framed shapes what citizens are willing to bear.

³¹On Ockham's Razor grounds, this is the simplest reading of Result 4 consistent with the data. A richer reading would require additional mechanism evidence that the partner declined to allow us to collect.

³²Bonomi, Gennaioli, and Tabellini (2021) make a related but distinct point for the United States: as economic shocks correlate income with cultural progressivism, voters switch from class to cultural identity, and political action becomes organized around the latter rather than the former. The Colombian observation we add is that, in a polarized post-conflict city, the protest itself can be orthogonal to every standing identity, and the engine of voice is the breadth of the trust budget.

8. Limitations

Like all research, this study has important limitations. We name them in a dedicated paragraph because the body of the paper, not a footnote, is the right place for them.

The first limitation is that we measure support, not participation. The partner declined to ask whether the respondent personally took part in the events of April to June. A respondent who reports a 10 on the support scale may have remained at home; a respondent who reports a 0 may have been on the front line. The patterns we document are patterns of expressed preference, not realized behavior. The translation from preference to behavior is itself a part of the hi-identifiers prediction (Van Zomeren et al., 2008), and we cannot test that translation with our data.

The second limitation is that the survey is cross-sectional. Identification is measured at the same time as support; we cannot rule out reverse causation, particularly for political identification, where attitudes toward the event are constitutive of the identity itself. CaliBRANDO has been running since 2014, and a panel extension that anchors identification in pre-strike measurements would substantially strengthen the design. We are working with the partner toward that extension.³³

The third limitation is the political-orientation measure. Our indirect instrument is a noisier signal of left-right placement than a direct scale would be. To the extent that the noise is symmetric, it attenuates the magnitude of the political-orientation coefficient (Result 1) and the political-identity coefficient (Result 4) toward zero; to the extent that it is asymmetric, it could bias the direction of those coefficients. We have no direct test of the asymmetry. The patterns we report are conservative in the symmetric case and uncertain in the asymmetric one.

The fourth limitation is sample composition. Respondents were recruited in public spaces. People who stayed home during the months after the strike, disproportionately older, female, and resident in the more violent comunas, are under-represented relative to the city's population. The CaliBRANDO weighting partly corrects for this. It does not correct for the unobserved characteristics that correlate with staying home and with both ingroup identification and support.

The fifth limitation is external validity. Cali in 2021 is a polarized post-conflict city after a spectacular violent event in a developing country with a long history of social uprising. We do not claim our finding generalizes to Hong Kong, where the relevant cleavage is between a politicized identity and a coercive state; to Pakistan, where the identity is anti-American; to the United States, where the cleavage is partisan and partisan identification is the relevant identity. We claim the finding generalizes to other Latin American cities (Santiago after October 2019, Quito after October 2019, La Paz after November 2019, Bogotá after November 2019) where the protest cut across rather than aligned with the city's standing demographic and political cleavages. The transportability is plausible there and uncertain elsewhere. The right next step is a coordinated multi-city version of the survey.

The sixth and final limitation is mechanism. We focus on the value channel of Buchan et al. (2011): social identification with a group increases the value the individual attaches to the group's welfare relative to her own. We do not test the expectations channel, because the partner declined the vignette experiment that would have let us elicit empirical and normative

³³CaliBRANDO has been running annually since 2014. A panel extension that anchors identification in pre-2021 waves is in progress; we report the cross-sectional 2021 wave in this paper.

expectations directly. A different study, in a setting in which the vignette is admissible, would be the natural complement.

9. Conclusion

We started with Hirschman. A society's capacity to renegotiate a fractured social contract depends on the willingness of enough of its citizens to bear the private cost of public voice. The dominant prediction in the social-identity literature is that strong identifiers are the engine of that willingness. Our evidence from Cali in October 2021, a few months after one of the most violent uprisings in Colombia's recent history, points the other way. Conditional on a rich set of socio-demographic and economic controls and on district fixed effects, respondents who report stronger trust in members of their own district, own class, own religion, or own political views than in an average Colombian are systematically less supportive of the uprising. Universalists are more supportive. The pattern survives a symmetric placebo across the riot-police and rioter divide and is not displaced by proximity to the violent events of April to June.

We have not claimed that the hi-identifiers literature is wrong. We have claimed that, in a setting where the politicized cleavage cuts across every ingroup rather than aligning with any of them, its prediction reverses. The reversal matters for theory because it locates a class of contexts (polarized post-conflict cities in the developing world) in which the engine of collective action is the breadth of the trust budget rather than the depth of the ingroup attachment. It matters for policy because it identifies the harder, slower investment in cross-group institutions as the one that returns the kind of citizen a fragile social contract eventually needs.

Hirschman ended his book by reminding the reader that voice is a residual category, hardest to study and easiest to over-claim. We end with the same caution. The data tell us who supports an uprising, not who shows up in the street. They tell us what the trust budget looks like a few months after the event, not what it looked like a few months before. They tell us about Cali, not about every polarized city in the world. Within those bounds, the evidence is clear enough. The Cali uprising was not the work of the city's strongest identifiers. It was the work of the residents whose trust extended past their own group, far enough to take in an average Colombian.³⁴

³⁴We are grateful to POLIS and to the Universidad ICESI team for keeping the survey in the field through a period in which face-to-face interviews carried real risks for enumerators. The risk tolerance we describe in Section 4 is a feature, not a flaw, of the collaboration. We are also grateful to the InterAmerican Development Bank for their generous funding, and to the 40 pollsters and the 2,750 residents of Cali who gave us 25 minutes of their time in October and November 2021. All errors are ours.

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